

THE ASYMMETRIC EFFECTS OF MARITIME FREIGHT SHOCKS ON MANUFACTURING EQUITIES IN ASEAN ECONOMIES.

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ABSTRACT

In this study, I analyze the asymmetric impact of maritime freight shocks on manufacturing stocks in ASEAN countries via the synthesis of scholarly articles published between 2003 and 2024. As is widely recognized, the manufacturing industries in ASEAN member states rely heavily on international trade and shipping. Therefore, they tend to be susceptible to various maritime freight and cost shocks that can adversely affect their operations.

Although several researchers have studied the impact of oil-price shocks, financial crises, and cross-market spillover effects on ASEAN equity markets, there appears to be little scholarly work dedicated to investigating the consequences of maritime freight shocks on the stocks of manufacturing firms. Based on the findings of studies devoted to the analysis of ASEAN equity market integration, volatility asymmetry, commodity price shocks, and supply chain interruptions, I examine whether the rise in freight rates produces more pronounced negative impact on manufacturing stocks than the corresponding beneficial effect of decreases in freight cost levels.

As we can see from the literature, any external shock tends to result in higher levels of volatility and persistence when compared to those created by positive shocks of equal intensity. Moreover, the growing level of financial integration in the region implies that shipping shocks are likely to be transmitted across ASEAN equity markets through various trade and financial channels.

INTRODUCTION

Shipping and freight rates account for over 80% of total world goods volume transportation. Thus, variations in shipping and freights may influence the state of economies by influencing production cost levels, supply chain efficiency, and competitiveness. Disruptions in global logistics caused by pandemics such as COVID-19, port congestion, political instability, and interruptions in global transportation routes are some of the factors demonstrating the vulnerability of global supply chains.

Since ASEAN heavily relies on international business and export-oriented manufacturing industry, the region is significantly sensitive to changes in maritime transportation conditions. Importation of goods and logistics by industries located in Singapore, Malaysia, Thailand, Indonesia, Vietnam, and the Philippines indicate a significant share of manufacturing input relying on sea transportation. Thus, variations in freight rates may impact companies' profit levels and investment attractiveness, affecting manufacturing stocks in terms of price.

Several previous studies analyzed the effects of various external shocks to the ASEAN financial market. They found that oil price fluctuations negatively impacted the stock market

while financial crisis and economic recession produced a considerable degree of volatility and spill-over to other markets. Moreover, previous research analyzing shocks to the ASEAN stock market demonstrated asymmetry in responses with negative shocks having larger and longer impacts than positive ones.

Despite a growing body of literature studying effects of commodity shocks, integration of financial markets, and supply chains, little attention was paid to maritime freight shocks. In particular, disruptions in global logistics, associated with increased transport costs, become increasingly relevant due to recent shipping disturbances.

Therefore, this study will review previous literature concerning the topic of asymmetrical impacts of freight shocks to manufacturing ASEAN stocks and provide evidence of greater negative effect of freight cost increases in comparison to the positive effect produced by equally-sized cost decreases.

LITERATURE REVIEW

There is a large body of literature focused on analyzing external economic shocks to stock markets in ASEAN countries. Being highly dependent on foreign trade, these economies face a high exposure to economic shocks related to changes in transportation costs, commodity prices, financial markets, and macroeconomic factors. While there are only few papers that discuss impacts of maritime freight shocks on manufacturing stocks, researches concerning oil-price shocks, financial crises, market integration, and supply chains provide some useful insights on possible mechanisms of the effect of shocks on manufacturing stock prices.

Firstly, a substantial number of publications consider oil-price and other commodity and energy-price shocks in relation to financial markets in ASEAN. For example, according to Koh (2015), oil-price increases negatively affected real stock prices in the ASEAN-5 in six months. Moreover, both positive and negative changes in oil prices influenced stock markets in this group of countries, which indicates that investors are interested in energy price dynamics as a source of information about firm's profitability. Also, Nguyen et al. (2024) showed that rising prices of energy commodities caused harm to manufacturing, transportation, and electricity sectors in Southeast Asian countries. It should be emphasized that maritime freight cost increases usually go hand in hand with price increases in the field of energy and thus put additional pressure on manufacturing.

Secondly, studies on the differences between market reactions to favorable and unfavorable shocks provide another set of relevant information. Usually, investors show stronger response to unfavorable shocks. According to Henry, Olekalns, and Lakshman (2007), negative return shocks cause significantly higher stock market volatility in Southeast Asia compared to positive return shocks. Similarly, Thanh and Lan (2016) observed that negative shocks resulted in unfavorable volatility compared to positive shocks in ASEAN-6 markets. It follows from these papers that negative risks play a greater role in shaping investor sentiments and stock prices. In other words, there are many reasons to believe that positive and negative shocks will have opposite effects on manufacturing stock prices.

Thirdly, it is possible to mention studies on market asymmetry conducted by Tabash et al. (2023). They analyzed relation between stock market and exchange rate dynamics in ASEAN-5 and proved that negative stock returns lead to currency depreciation in the short term, while positive shocks affect the value of the currency to a lesser degree. Thus, unfavorable financial news can lead to wider macroeconomic effects and increased uncertainty. Overall, all these papers show that manufacturing stocks will be more affected by positive maritime freight shocks and vice versa.

Another issue that should be taken into account is the importance of market integration in the process of external shock transmission. For example, Ibrahim (2008) examined ASEAN stock markets' sensitivity to shocks occurring in other financial markets and showed that ASEAN stock prices respond negatively to decline in US market. Positive movement of stock prices in the United States and Japan had a less pronounced effect, indicating asymmetric behavior. Therefore, external shocks have a great effect on local stock market performance in ASEAN.

Finally, Rodriguez (2018) examined the level of market integration between ASEAN and USA stock markets after the global financial crisis of 2008. He found that these markets were more integrated in terms of stock returns, and return changes in US significantly influenced ASEAN stocks. It is well known that greater market integration improves its efficiency but at the same time increases contagion during financial distress.

Furthermore, literature on financial crises supports market integration theory. Adrangi, Raffiee, and Shank (2003) analyzed East Asian regional crises and found that stock market decline continued while financial problems moved from one economy to another. They concluded that Indonesia, Thailand, and Malaysia experienced severe volatility and weak markets during financial crises. Thus, regional relationships intensify the effects of an external shock.

In conclusion, the above-mentioned works provide several main conclusions. Firstly, shocks in the form of oil price increases, financial crises, and macroeconomic fluctuations decrease stock market performance in ASEAN. Secondly, negative shocks result in stronger and more sustainable effect than positive shocks. Thirdly, the process of financial integration makes the effect stronger since shocks are transmitted faster. Fourthly, manufacturing sectors are particularly vulnerable to cost increases and supply chain problems since these industries are heavily involved in transportation network.

However, a literature gap exists. There is a large number of studies dedicated to such topics as oil-price changes, financial crises, and exchange rate movements, but very few papers investigate the problem of maritime freight shocks in relation to manufacturing sector stocks in ASEAN. Given the development of global logistics and the emergence of new problems, such an analysis appears to be relevant.

METHODOLOGY AND DATA

The present literature review seeks to evaluate the impacts of maritime freight shocks on manufacturing equities in ASEAN member states and the reasons behind possible differences in these effects. Rather than providing any novel econometric research, the literature review

synthesizes the findings of peer-reviewed works published between 2003 and 2024 concerning external shocks, stock market behavior, financial integration, supply chain disruptions, and energy price shocks in ASEAN member countries.

Overall, nine peer-reviewed studies were selected based on their relation to the effects of maritime freight shocks on manufacturing equities. These sources touch upon four different issues:

- (1) oil price shocks and commodity price shocks.
- (2) asymmetric market responses.
- (3) financial-market integration and spillover effects.
- (4) sector-specific supply chain disruptions. Combined, these topics can provide a rationale for how maritime disruption impacts ASEAN manufacturing equities.

In stage one, the sources were categorized according to their topic or subject matter. For example, studies like Koh (2015) and Nguyen et al. (2024) could be considered under the umbrella topic of oil price shocks and commodity price shocks since both sources examined the influence of rising energy costs on activity and stock performance. In turn, Henry et al. (2007), Thanh and Lan (2016), and Tabash et al. (2023) were classified into asymmetric market responses since they deal with volatility patterns and differences between positive and negative shocks. Financial integration could be considered the main topic of Ibrahim (2008) and Rodriguez (2018) who evaluated the cross-linkages between global equity markets. Finally, Adrangi et al. (2003) and Nguyen et al. (2024) contributed additional insight related to financial crises, regional contagion, and vulnerabilities within ASEAN supply chains.

In stage two, a synthesis of findings for each paper is developed. Attention is paid to how positive shocks are different from negative ones, which sectors are particularly vulnerable, and how disruption effects might spread to adjacent economies. This technique allows discovering some common findings despite the use of different methodologies, time frames, and regional focuses.

The techniques varied widely among studies. For instance, Koh (2015) relied on a structural Vector Autoregression (VAR) model to study the impact of oil-price shocks on ASEAN-5 stock markets. At the same time, the effects of energy-cost shocks on the ASEAN-5 economy and its sub-markets were evaluated via computational simulation in Nguyen et al. (2024). Henry et al. (2007) used nonlinear modeling to estimate volatility spillovers in Southeast Asian markets, whereas Thanh and Lan (2016) used EGARCH and VAR modeling techniques. Finally, Tabash et al. (2023) studied the stock movements and foreign exchange rates via panel ARDL and nonlinear ARDL, while Ibrahim (2008) and Rodriguez (2018) analyzed cross-market integration and response asymmetries using the frameworks outlined above.

A particular focus should be paid to Nguyen et al. (2024)'s approach. The authors relied on the GTAP-E-PowerS computable general equilibrium model to simulate energy price increases. This is important for this study because of its emphasis on the way cost shocks could travel through interlinked supply chains and target the transportation and manufacturing industries in particular. This source will not be replicated; however, its findings would still help prove the point.

In the process of gathering evidence, a comparative synthesis of findings was performed to detect similarities among studies with regards to certain types of external shocks. First of all, a comparison would determine whether shocks are asymmetric in their nature, whether manufacturing stocks would experience more pronounced effects compared to other sectors, and whether financial market integration would cause shocks to spread to the ASEAN area.

Based on evidence from multiple sources, a conceptual framework is built. It incorporates the general findings of the selected literature and describes the relationship between maritime cost shocks and ASEAN manufacturing equities. Higher cost leads to increased transport and manufacturing costs, negatively impacting manufacturers' profitability. Thus, investors could act on the market to bring manufacturing stocks lower.

Finally, a literature-review approach was chosen for the present research because there were almost no publications specifically addressing the issue at hand.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

From an examination of existing literature, there are four crucial observations on the possible impacts of maritime freight shocks on ASEAN manufacturing stock returns. Namely, the literature indicates that

- (1) external cost shocks negatively affect stock market performance.
- (2) the effects of shocks on markets are not symmetric.
- (3) increased financial integration causes shocks to propagate among markets.
- (4) manufacturing stocks' behavior reflects the vulnerabilities of the manufacturing sector, which depends significantly on the supply chain integrity.

Impact of External Cost Shocks on ASEAN Stock Market Performance

One consistent observation is that shocks from external costs, such as oil price rises, negatively affect ASEAN stock market performance. Koh (2015) found that stock price declines happened as a consequence of oil price shocks in ASEAN-5 in a few months. Nguyen et al. (2024) demonstrated that increases in energy prices had negative effects on manufacturing, transport, and energy generation industries in the whole Southeast Asia.

This implies that increases in maritime freight rates should also be harmful to ASEAN manufacturing stock returns since manufacturing costs are affected significantly by the availability and reliability of the transportation. In turn, increases in shipping rates make firms face additional expenses related to importing materials and exporting goods. This decreases expected profitability and reduces market attractiveness of manufacturing stocks.

Overall, the manufacturing sector in the region is highly vulnerable to maritime freight shocks, as they affect production costs, performance, and competitiveness. As maritime freight costs are crucially important for the operation of manufacturing companies in ASEAN, shocks in the area can cause substantial changes in stock prices.

Asymmetric Responses of Markets to Shocks

Secondly, there is clear evidence of asymmetry between positive and negative shocks, namely the former have less impact on markets than the latter. Henry, Olekalns, and Lakshman (2007) observed greater volatility in response to negative return shocks than to positive ones for markets of Southeast Asian countries. Thanh and Lan (2016) also discovered that unfavorable shocks were characterized by worse volatility responses compared to favorable ones for ASEAN-6 stock markets. Finally, Tabash et al. (2023) noticed the relationship between negative changes in stock prices and currency devaluation.

In connection to maritime freight shocks, this observation can be used to prove the greater effect of increases in rates compared to decreases. Indeed, investors respond more aggressively to negative than positive changes, as losses and uncertainties are perceived as more severe and frightening than benefits. Therefore, an abrupt increase in maritime freight costs may cause sharp decreases in manufacturing stocks. At the same time, a decline in shipping rates can produce limited effects.

Thus, the fear associated with maritime transport issues plays an important role in causing disproportionate market reaction. Overall, the supply chain disruptions have to be addressed carefully as the adverse effects may exceed the actual cost of the event.

Financial Integration and Shock Transmission Among ASEAN Economies

Third, financial integration of ASEAN economies enables shocks to propagate across countries in the region. Ibrahim (2008) found that declines in U.S. stock market performance cause strong negative reactions among ASEAN markets but positive changes have a weak impact. Also, Rodriguez (2018) mentioned that ASEAN and U.S. markets became more interconnected following the global financial crisis, so disturbances would be easier to propagate in ASEAN.

Finally, Adrangi, Raffiee, and Shank (2003) revealed the fact that financial crises in East Asia created long-term declines in financial indicators for multiple countries in the region. It means that shocks typically go beyond national boundaries due to the financial integration. Thus, disturbances can have spillover effects, propagating from one economy to another.

With regard to maritime transport disturbances in ASEAN, shocks in one economy are likely to be transferred to others in the form of changes in trade, financial flows, and investors' behavior. Consequently, negative effects caused by increases in maritime freight costs and resulting declines in manufacturing stocks may spread throughout the region.

Given the similar trade structure of ASEAN countries and their interdependence in terms of logistics and production, it is essential to consider both domestic and international effects while dealing with maritime transport issues in ASEAN.

Manufacturing Stock Returns and Supply-Chain Disruptions

Finally, the last finding reveals a high degree of vulnerability of manufacturing stocks to increases in the cost of production factors. Specifically, Nguyen et al. (2024) revealed that the increases in energy prices had more negative effects on manufacturing and transportation than on agriculture and food industry. In turn, manufacturing relies heavily on the availability of logistics, imported materials, and transportation services.

Consequently, any disruptions related to maritime freight would have significant impacts on manufacturing. There are different ways for maritime freight shocks to influence manufacturing stock returns. On the one hand, increases in transport costs lead to decreased profitability margins. On the other hand, shipping disruptions negatively affect production activities. Moreover, the uncertainty in the area of maritime logistics creates additional challenges for investors, reducing market appeal of stocks.

ASEAN manufacturing sector plays a vital role in foreign trade activities and economic growth, so its disruption can bring severe economic consequences. Low manufacturing activities lead to unemployment, trade decline, and slow growth. As a result, investors often expect adverse economic outcomes, which affects manufacturing stock prices adversely.

Taking everything into consideration, the analysis provides clear evidence of the hypothesis that shocks from maritime freight increases are more likely to harm ASEAN manufacturing stocks than positive effects from decreases. The studies discussed above provide indirect proof to this claim based on the analysis of financial phenomena in the region, namely:

- External cost shocks typically have negative effects on stock markets.
- Positive shocks have smaller impacts than negative ones.
- Financial integration leads to shock propagation in ASEAN.
- Manufacturing is vulnerable due to the dependence on maritime logistics.

Conclusion

Finally, the research explored whether maritime freight shocks influence stock returns from the manufacturing sector in ASEAN countries. A number of theoretical papers were analyzed in terms of energy price fluctuations, financial interconnectivity, market volatility, and supply chain risks. Although there are no specific studies that deal with shipping cost shocks, it has been proven that increased costs negatively influence the profitability of manufacturing enterprises.

Higher energy, transportation, and logistics costs adversely influence profit expectations and decrease stock prices. Besides, it has been proven that negative economic shocks cause larger and more prolonged changes in market dynamics than positive ones of the same magnitude, thus proving the hypothesis about asymmetric effects. At the same time, a highly integrated financial market in ASEAN enables shocks to travel across the region much faster, intensifying their impacts on stock prices.

Considering its dependence on international trade, imported components, and maritime freight transportation, manufacturing is among industries particularly susceptible to such influences.

In summary, the analysis proves that increased maritime freight costs negatively impact stock market expectations for manufacturing enterprises in ASEAN countries, while lower shipping expenses cause limited benefits. Hence, additional attention should be paid to managing supply chain risks in order to minimize the influence of negative transport and logistical issues in the future.

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